

EXCALIBUR

Preserving the Past, Unveiling the Future.

Advanced Toolkits for Enhanced Study, Conservation, and Restoration in Burial Excavations and Findings

EXCALIBUR is a **HorizonEU project** that creates a holistic framework of innovative, **open-source digital tools (AI, Machine Learning, XR)** for the enhanced study, conservation, and restoration of cultural heritage objects using their Digital Twins

FOUR LEVELS OF CULTURAL HERITAGE

EXCALIBUR advanced methods are applied across **four layers** of cultural heritage:

Burial sites, excavations, and surroundings

Tomb structures and burial decoration

Artefacts, burial findings, traditions and ceremonies

Human and burial remains

FROM LAB TO FIELD: TOOLKITS IN PILOT SITES

EXCALIBUR toolkits are implemented and validated in four real-world pilot use cases:

Tomb of the Kings
(Paphos, Cyprus)

Tomb of the Egyptian
(Sulky, Sardinia, Italy)

The State Museum of Egyptian Art
(Munich, Germany)

The Bioarchaeological Collection of DUTH
(Komotini, Greece)

OPEN CALL: FINANCIAL SUPPORT TO THIRD PARTIES

Are you a heritage institution, SME, or researcher? EXCALIBUR is offering **€400,000** to support your digital conservation efforts.

The project will award **8 lump-sum grants of €50,000 each** to third parties to test, validate, and enhance EXCALIBUR digital tools and methodologies in real-world cultural heritage scenarios.

KEY FACTS ABOUT THE PROJECT

Call: HORIZON-CL2-2024-HERITAGE-ECCCH-01-05

Type of Action: Innovation Action (IA)

Project number: 101233712

Total EU Contribution: € 3 995 408,13

Duration: 42 months

Project Coordinator: Brain, Health & Virtual Reality (BHV) Research Group, Centre for Research & Technology Hellas – CERTH, Information Technologies Institute

echoes
European Cloud
for Heritage Open Science

EXCALIBUR is part of the ECCCH Cultural Heritage Cloud initiative, managed by the ECHOES project

PROJECT PARTNERS

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www.excalibur-eccch.eu

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